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STUDENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT

J. M. Moita
BEST, Portugal

Topics: Diversity in Engineering Education, Strong demand for democratic involvement in educational processes

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The proposed workshop has the following main goals: first of all, demonstrating to professors, researchers and experts why it is relevant to gather the students' input regarding educational matters; secondly, presenting the work developed by BEST in order to close the feedback-loop between education providers and students; and finally, understanding the way lecturers could be key players in the process of implementing the proposed changes. Participants will have the opportunity to think critically about their own teaching and evaluation practices, reflect on the main challenges faced when trying to implement changes and understand how their peers and students perceive them. By doing so, participants are expected to become more aware of existing flaws, both in their work and the current teaching and evaluation practices, and increase their openness towards actively gathering and implementing feedback from the relevant stakeholders.

Board of European Students of Technology (BEST) is a European non-profit organisation celebrating, in 2019, three decades of a history full of continuous efforts to involve students in the improvement of STEM Education. With the vision of Empowering Diversity, which is closely connected with the conference thematic "Diversity in Engineering Education", BEST has been involving students in Engineering Education and actively disseminating their opinions to relevant stakeholders. With 23 years of experience in participating in European projects and attending international Education conferences, BEST wants to bring forward the perspectives of students as a key element in educational decision making and also to understand how professors, researchers and experts perceive this demand.

In terms of format and dynamics, the workshop will be similar to the sessions held in BEST Symposia on Education (BSEs), so that participants will experience the methodology used by BEST to gather the students' opinions in these events. After the introduction, self and hetero-evaluation exercises will be conducted, in order to identify problems and improvement points in teaching methods and practices. Divided into groups, participants will be brainstorming and discussing possible solutions to the identified problems. Later on, the solutions found during the previous exercise will be

discussed and worked upon by all the participants together, in order to reach outcomes that all professors can implement in their own classrooms.

To finalise the workshop, the problems found by professors will be compared to the ones identified by students from different European countries. Through this exercise, professors will understand whether their self-assessment diverges from students' views. It will be a way to increase their motivation and interest in understanding and fulfilling students' needs and expectations, and a chance to take action towards this. The workshop impact on the participants will be assessed, as the participants are expected to better understand how they can have an active role in involving students more effectively. After the conference, the workshop outcomes will be analysed and reported by BEST members in order to improve the way the organisation connects with experts.